

BIODT
biodiversitydigitaltwin

From Data to Digital Twins: Empowering Biodiversity Digital Twins with Research Infrastructures

Report of webinar May 2025

Introduction

The final webinar of the BioDT project brought together four leading biodiversity Research Infrastructures (RIs) - GBIF, eLTER, DiSSCo, and LifeWatch ERIC - to reflect on three years of collaboration. The event explored how these RIs contributed to the development of BioDT's prototype Digital Twins (pDTs), shared what they gained from the project, and offered perspectives on future opportunities and challenges.

The session highlighted the critical role of research infrastructures in data provision, model validation, and fostering interoperability for more sustainable, science-based policy tools.

Highlights from the RIs

GBIF

(The Global Biodiversity Information Facility)

GBIF focused on the significance of biodiversity occurrence data and its role as the backbone for building reliable Digital Twins. The representative discussed how GBIF supported BioDT by providing extensive, standardised biodiversity datasets and aligning with FAIR data principles. The cooperation with BioDT allowed GBIF to better understand emerging requirements for real-time modelling and integration with HPC infrastructures. During the event, it was also noted the importance of streamlining data access for predictive biodiversity modelling and integrating with platforms like Destination Earth.

eLTER

(Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research)

eLTER highlighted how their network of long-term ecological observatories and socio-ecological data flows into BioDT's models. They contributed by facilitating site-specific metadata and long-term monitoring data, which are essential for understanding changes in biodiversity over time. Their involvement in BioDT enhanced their visibility within digital twin dialogues and opened new channels for collaboration with HPC platforms. They also addressed challenges in aligning heterogeneous environmental data with digital twin workflows and stressed the need for ongoing support for data harmonisation efforts.

DiSSCo

(Distributed System of Scientific Collections)

DiSSCo presented its role in integrating specimen-based data into the BioDT infrastructure. The focus was on linking physical specimens with digital biodiversity models to enable traceability, reproducibility, and richer metadata annotations. DiSSCo's contribution enabled BioDT to tap into verified biological records from natural history collections. They noted how BioDT strengthened awareness about the importance of linking physical and digital infrastructures and the need for improving interoperability with emerging tools and standards.

LifeWatch ERIC

LifeWatch ERIC underscored its dual role as both a contributor of biodiversity data and a future host of the BioDT platform. LifeWatch ERIC offered modelling environments and analytical services that supported the development of BioDT's pDTs. LifeWatch ERIC also shared insights into planned next steps, including their commitment to maintaining the BioDT platform and integrating it within the LifeWatch service catalogue. Their engagement with BioDT expanded their service offerings and advanced their alignment with European HPC and digital twin strategies.

Q&A and Closing Reflections

During the final Q&A session, participants raised questions about:

- 🐾 Long-term sustainability of Digital Twins within RI infrastructures
- 🐾 Strategies to improve FAIR data compliance across different ecosystems
- 🐾 Synergies between BioDT and other European data and digital twin initiatives
- 🐾 Opportunities to scale successful pDTs into operational services

All panellists agreed on the importance of co-designing digital twins with RI users and policymakers, ensuring ongoing collaboration and improving communication around data use and credit.

Conclusion

The final BioDT webinar demonstrated how digital twin innovation thrives on strong partnerships with research infrastructures. The cooperation across GBIF, eLTER, DiSSCo, and LifeWatch ERIC exemplifies a scalable model for future initiatives aiming to integrate biodiversity data into advanced modelling environments.

BioDT's legacy includes not only technological advancements but also strengthened connections between digital innovation and biodiversity science - laying a solid foundation for future integration within the Destination Earth initiative and broader EU data ecosystems.

Did you miss the webinar?

The full webinar recording is available on the BioDT YouTube channel.

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